

MAPLE MATEMATIK PAKETIDA FUNKSIYALARNI TEYLOR QATORIGA YOYISHGA OID MISOLLARNI YECHISH.

Jumagul Vohobjon qizi Mirzaahmedova
Andijon davlat universiteti tayanch doktoranti

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada elementar funksiyalarni Teylor qatoriga yoyishni matematik teoremlar, formulalar orqali hisoblash va Maple matematik paketida misollarni yechish bosqichlari haqida ma’lumotlar keltirilgan.

Kalit so’zlar: funksiya, Teylor, qator, series, matematik paketlar, Maple, darajali qator.

$f(x)$ funksiyani birorta darajali qatorning yig`indisi ko`rinishida ifodalashga berilgan **funksiyani qatorga yoyish** deb ataladi. Faraz qilaylik, $f(x)$ funksiya biror $(-r, r)$ da istalgan tartibdagi hosilalarga ega bo’lsin [1].

1-teorema. Agar $\exists M > 0, \forall x \in (-r, r), \forall n \geq 0$ da

$$|f^{(n)}(x)| \leq M$$

Bo’lsa, $f(x)$ funksiya $(-r, r)$ da Teylor qatoriga yoyiladi:

$$f(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{f^{(n)}(0)}{n!} x^n = f(0) + \frac{f'(0)}{1!} x + \frac{f''(0)}{2!} x^2 + \dots + \frac{f^{(n)}(0)}{n!} x^n + \dots \quad (1)$$

Ma’lumki, $f(x)$ funksiyaning Lagranj ko’rinishidagi qoldiq hadli Teylor formulasi quyidagicha bo’ladi:

$$f(x) = f(0) + \frac{f'(0)}{1!} x + \frac{f''(0)}{2!} x^2 + \dots + \frac{f^{(n)}(0)}{n!} x^n + r_n(x),$$

Bunda,

$$r_n(x) = \frac{f^{(n)}(\theta x)}{(n+1)!} x^{n+1} \quad (0 < \theta < 1).$$

Teoremaning shartidan foydalanib topamiz:

$$|r_n(x)| = \left| \frac{f^{(n)}(\theta x)}{(n+1)!} x^{n+1} \right| \leq M \cdot \frac{r^{n+1}}{(n+1)!} \quad (x \in (-r, r)).$$

Ravshanki,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{r^{n+1}}{(n+1)!} = 0.$$

Demak, $\forall x \in (-r, r)$ da

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} r_n(x) = 0$$

Bo’lib, undan qaralayotgan $f(x)$ funksiyaning Teylor qatoriga yoyilishi kelib chiqadi [2].

Matematik hisoblashlarni, sodda va murakkab amallarni bajarishga, kompyuter modelini tuzishga mo’ljallangan dasturlash paketlari va muhitlari mavjud bo’lib, ularni har birining imkoniyatlari alohida o’rin tutadi. Matematik paketlar sarasiga kiruvchi Maple 12 dasturida funksiyalarni hisoblash jarayonini ko’rib chiqamiz. Dastlab dasturni ishga tushiramiz, “File” menyusi ⇒ “Save as” bo’limini tanlaymiz ⇒ hosil bo’lgan oynadan faylga nom berib saqlab olamiz [3].

1-rasm. Maple 12 matematik paketini ishchi oynasi.

1-misol. $\sqrt{x}$ sodda funksiyani Teylor qatoriga yoyish bosqichini amalga oshiramiz. Barcha matematik ifodalar ishchi oynaning o’ng tomonidagi uskunalar paneli orqali kiritib olinadi. Maple dasturida $\sqrt{x}$ ushbu funksiyamiz $\text{sqrt}(x)$ ko’rinishda yoziladi [5].

$\text{sqrt}(x)$ yozilib Enter tugmasi bosiladi, keyingi qatorda $\sqrt{x}$ hosil bo’ladi, ushbu funksiya ustiga sichqonchani olib borib o’ng tomonini bir marta chertamiz, hosil bo’lgan yordamchi oynadan Series ⇒ Series ⇒ x bo’limini tanlaymiz [3].

2-rasm. Berilgan funsiyani qatorga bo’lish bo’limlari

3-rasm. Qator parametrlarini kiritish oynasi.

Series expansion point $\Rightarrow$ qator kengayish nuqtasi=50

Series order $\Rightarrow$ qator tartibi=5

Katachalarga kerakli qiymatlar kiritilib Ok tugmasi bosiladi.

4-rasm. $\sqrt{x}$ funsiyani qatorga bo’lingan natijasi.

2-misol. Ushbu funsiyani Teylor qatoriga yoyishni ko’rib chiqamiz.

$$f(x) = \ln \frac{1+x}{1-x}$$

ma’lumki,

$$\ln \frac{1+x}{1-x} = \ln(1+x) - \ln(1-x)$$

bo'ladi.

Biz yuqorida

$$\ln(1+x) = x - \frac{x^2}{2} + \frac{x^3}{3} - \dots + (-1)^{n-1} \frac{x^n}{n} + \dots$$

$$\ln(1-x) = -x - \frac{x^2}{2} - \frac{x^3}{3} - \dots - \frac{x^n}{n} - \dots$$

Bo'lishini ko'rgan edik. Bu munosabatlardan foydalanib topamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \ln(1+x) - \ln(1-x) &= x - \frac{x^2}{2} + \frac{x^3}{3} - \dots + (-1)^{n-1} \frac{x^n}{n} + \dots \\ &- \left(-x - \frac{x^2}{2} - \frac{x^3}{3} - \dots - \frac{x^n}{n} - \dots \right) = 2x + \frac{2x^3}{3} + \frac{2x^5}{5} + \dots + \frac{2x^{2n-1}}{2n-1} + \dots \end{aligned}$$

Demak,

$$\ln \frac{1+x}{1-x} = 2 \left(x + \frac{x^3}{3} + \frac{x^5}{5} + \dots + \frac{x^{2n-1}}{2n-1} + \dots \right). \quad (2)$$

(10) darajali qatorning yaqinlashish radiusi $r=1$ bo'lib, yaqinlashish to'plamsi $(-1,1)$ bo'ladi.

The screenshot shows a software window with a menu bar (File, Edit, Drawing, Plot, Animations) and a toolbar. The main window displays the expression $\ln\left(\frac{1-x}{1+x}\right)$ and its series expansion in x . The expansion is given as:

$$\ln\left(\frac{99}{101}\right) - I \operatorname{csgn}\left(\frac{1(1-x)}{1+x}\right) \pi + \frac{2}{9999} (x-100) - \frac{200}{99980001} (x-100)^2 + \frac{60002}{2999100089997} (x-100)^3 - \frac{2000200}{9996000599960001} (x-100)^4 + \frac{1000200002}{499750049995000249995} (x-100)^5 - \frac{60020000600}{2998200449940004499820003} (x-100)^6 + O((x-100)^7)$$

5-rasm. Natija

3-misol. Ushbu

$$f(x) = \int_0^x \frac{\sin t}{t} dt$$

funksiya Teylor qatoriga yoyilsin.

ma'lumki,

$$\sin t = t - \frac{t^3}{3!} + \frac{t^5}{5!} - \dots + (-1)^{n-1} \frac{t^{2n-1}}{(2n-1)!} + \dots$$

Unda

$$\frac{\sin t}{t} = 1 - \frac{t^2}{3!} + \frac{t^4}{5!} - \dots + (-1)^{n-1} \frac{t^{2n-2}}{(2n-1)!} + \dots$$

bo'ladi. Bu darajali qatorni hadlab integrallab topamiz:

$$\int_0^x \frac{\sin t}{t} dt = \int_0^x \left(1 - \frac{t^2}{3!} + \frac{t^4}{5!} - \dots + (-1)^{n-1} \frac{t^{2n-2}}{(2n-1)!} + \dots \right) dt =$$

$$= x - \frac{x^3}{3! \cdot 3} + \frac{x^5}{5! \cdot 5} - \dots + (-1)^{n-1} \frac{x^{2n-1}}{(2n-1)! \cdot (2n-1)} + \dots$$

Keyingi darajali qatorning yaqinlashish radiusi $r = +\infty$ bo'ladi.

(1)

(2)

6-rasm. Natija.

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